

The Influence of Knowledge Management on The Culture of Knowledge Sharing in The Ministry of Religion in Binjai City

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of knowledge management on the culture of sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with a total of 105 people taken using proportional sampling. The research results show that knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on sharing culture. This is shown by the T-count value of T-count of 19.564 > t table 1.65978, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if knowledge management is increased by 1 unit, then sharing culture will increase by 0.644 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.786 or 78.60%, which indicates that knowledge management has a high influence on sharing culture, while the remaining 21.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on the culture of sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City. It identifies that improvements in knowledge management can contribute to an enhanced sharing culture.

Keywords: knowledge management; sharing culture

INTRODUCTION

In an era of globalization and increasingly intense competition, organizations, including government agencies such as the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City, must continue to adapt and improve their performance. Knowledge management has been recognized as one of the key factors that can help organizations optimize their resources and create sustainable added value (Sihite, 2018). In the context of government institutions, knowledge management is becoming increasingly important to support effective service provision and meet community needs (Lestari & Santoso, 2022)

In the midst of the dynamics of rapid change, government institutions such as the Binjai City Ministry of Religion not only face pressure to continue to adapt, but also to ensure that the services they provide remain relevant and effective in meeting community needs. In this context, knowledge management becomes increasingly important because it enables government institutions to increase operational efficiency, overcome complex challenges related to religion, morality, and public policy, improve the quality of public services, and promote innovation in religious service and development activities (Sedarmayanti & Nurliawati, 2012). Thus, knowledge management is not just about storing and managing information, but also about creating an environment where knowledge can be shared, accessed and utilized effectively to achieve organizational goals (Qisty, 2022 CE). In the context of government institutions, this also means strengthening transparency, accountability and responsiveness to the needs of diverse communities. The Binjai City

Ministry of Religion, as a government institution responsible for managing religious affairs at the local level, requires an effective approach in managing knowledge to support the organization's mission and vision and meet community needs. In this context, it is important to understand the influence of Knowledge Management on the culture of knowledge sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City.

Based on the results of the author's initial observations, there are phenomena that occur that can be identified related to knowledge management and the culture of sharing knowledge in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City. Although knowledge management is considered important, there are obstacles in accessing and utilizing available knowledge. Some employees do not have sufficient access to or adequate understanding of the systems or platforms used to share knowledge. In addition, an organizational culture that does not encourage or even inhibits a culture of knowledge sharing can be a major barrier to effective knowledge management. According to (Tupamahu et al., 2021) states that knowledge sharing is the behavior of individuals sharing what they have learned and transferring what they know, to those who have common interests and have found the knowledge useful.

Temporary (Partogi & Tjahjawati, 2019) states that knowledge sharing is a process of sharing and distributing knowledge between one individual and another which can be useful for stimulating each individual to think more creatively and effectively. In this research, the meaning of knowledge sharing refers to opinions (Nurcahyo & Wikaningrum, 2020) is a series of joint learning processes by sharing knowledge between employees involving one individual and another involving experiences that can be used as a source for sharing knowledge. To measure the culture of sharing knowledge in this research, there are several indicators used by previous studies, including research conducted by Chuang in (Nurcahyo & Wikaningrum, 2020) that is :

- 1) Willingness to share specialized knowledge,
- 2) Willingness to share knowledge virtually;
- 3) Willingness to give advice in work;
- 4) Willingness to discuss during meetings;
- 5) Willingness to share experiences as a solution.

Many factors can influence the culture of knowledge sharing. In this study, researchers limited themselves to knowledge management variables. Knowledge Management is a process for disseminating, capturing and utilizing existing knowledge as a form of maintaining an organization's competitive advantage (Millmore et al., 2007). Meanwhile, according to (Dalkir, 2005) that knowledge management is a systematic coordination within an organization that manages human resources, technology, processes and organizational structure in order to increase value through reuse and innovation. This coordination can be achieved through creating, sharing and applying knowledge using experience and actions that the company has taken for the continuity of organizational learning. In this study the researcher refers to opinions (Millmore et al., 2007) in defining Knowledge Management, namely the process of disseminating, capturing and utilizing existing knowledge as a form of maintaining the competitive advantage of an organization To measure the Knowledge

Management variable in this research the author refers to opinion theory (Millmore et al., 2007) that is :

1. Identifying Relevant Knowledge;
2. Knowledge Acquisition and Retention
3. Sharing knowledge
4. Use of Knowledge in Decision Making
5. Knowledge Development and Innovation;
6. Knowledge Management Performance Measurement and Evaluation;
7. Organizational Culture that Encourages Learning and Knowledge Sharing.

This research aims to analyze and identify the influence of knowledge management on the culture of knowledge sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Binjai City Ministry of Religion, Child Protection and Community Office. The time this research was carried out was from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City with a total of 155 employees with the following details.

Table 1. Population details at the Binjai City Ministry of Religion Office

No.	Status	Number of people)
1.	ASN	94
2.	Honorary	10
3.	Security officer	1
Amount		105

Source: Ministry of Religion, Binjai City 2024

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to Sugiyono (2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique when all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 105 employees. The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0. Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable. The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Sharing culture

X = Knowledge management

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Knowledge Management (X), on the dependent variable, namely Sharing Culture (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research results

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Knowledge management	105	3.40	5.00	4.3867	.47496
Sharing culture	105	3.00	5.00	4.3448	.48158
Valid N (listwise)	105				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents rated knowledge management and sharing culture in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City as above average, with mean values of 4.3867 and 4.3448 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.4749 for Knowledge management and 0.4815 for Sharing culture), indicating that although there are individual differences in perceptions, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Knowledge Management Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.814 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.931 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.880 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.887 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X5	0.887 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X6	0.858 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X7	0.843 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the Knowledge Management variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.1918 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Knowledge Management variable are valid.(Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Sharing Culture Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.807 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.791 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.897 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.825 > 0.1918	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 1.942 + 0.644X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 1.942 means that if there is no knowledge management, then there is a sharing culture of 1.942 points. The knowledge management regression coefficient is 0.644, meaning that knowledge management influences an increase in sharing culture by 0.644 for every 1 point increase

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.888a	.788	.786	1.11418

a. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge management

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.786 or 78.60%, which means that knowledge management has a high influence on sharing culture, while the remaining 31.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of knowledge management on the culture of sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City

Ha: There is an influence of knowledge management on the culture of sharing in the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,942	1,017		1,910	,059
	Knowledge management	,644	,033	,888	19,564	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Sharing culture

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $19.564 > t$ table 1.65978, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected, and Ha is accepted or there is a positive but not significant influence between knowledge management and sharing culture in the Ministry of Religion. Binjai City.

Discussion

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Knowledge Management on Knowledge Sharing Culture, these findings are in line with research results from (Sari, 2022) which shows that sharing management has a positive and significant effect on employee sharing culture. The implications of these findings indicate that investment in knowledge management systems and practices can strengthen collaboration and knowledge transfer between employees. This can lead to increased operational efficiency, faster innovation, and improved overall organizational performance (Asbari & Novitasari, 2020). By understanding that a culture of knowledge sharing is influenced by knowledge management, organizations can focus more on strategies that encourage the exchange of information and experience, such as training, appropriate use of information technology, and creating a work environment that supports collaboration. Overall, the implications of these findings emphasize the importance of knowledge management as a key factor in creating a dynamic and adaptive organizational culture (Abubakar, 2019).

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of hypothesis testing show that knowledge management has a positive but not significant effect on sharing culture. This can be seen from the T-count value of 19.564 > t table 1.65978, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This regression coefficient shows that if knowledge management is increased by 1 unit, the change in sharing culture as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.644 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Ministry of Religion of Binjai City
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.786 or 78.60%, which means that knowledge management has a high influence on sharing culture, while the remaining 21.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the research results, discussions and conclusions that have been explained, here are several suggestions that can be given to institutions, especially the Binjai City Ministry of Religion Office:

1. Institutions are advised to develop knowledge management systems by adopting appropriate information technology, as well as holding regular training for employees to encourage effective knowledge sharing.
2. Institutions are advised to organize leadership training programs that focus on communication skills and knowledge management, so that leaders can encourage

employees to be actively involved in sharing knowledge and creating a collaborative work environment.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, AM (2019). Knowledge management, decision-making style and organizational performance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*.
- Asbari, M., & Novitasari, D. (2020). The Influence of Knowledge Sharing and Cultural Mediation Activities on Teacher Innovation Ability. *Journal of Educational Management and Supervision*.
- Auliana, S., & Nurasiah, I. (2018). Application of Knowledge Management in the Higher Education Data Reporting Process. *Indonesian Journal of Strategic Management*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.25134/ijsm.v1i1.838>
- Azeem, M., Ahmed, M., Haider, S., & Sajjad, M. (2021). Expanding competitive advantage through organizational culture, knowledge sharing and organizational innovation. *Technology in Society*, 66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101635>
- Dalkir, K. (2005). *Knowledge Management In Theory and Practice*. House, Jordan Hill, Oxford OX2 8DP.
- Fahmi, I. (2013). *Performance Management, Theory and Applications*. Alfabeta.
- Ghozali & Latan. (2015). *Concepts, Techniques, Applications Using Smart PLS 3.0 for Empirical Research*. BP Undip. Semarang Harnanto. 2017. *Cost Accounting: Historical Cost Systems*. BPF.
- Ghozali, Imam & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Squares "Engineering Concepts and Applications Using the Smart PLS 3.0 Program"*. Diponegoro University.
- Handiman, U. (2023). *Strategic Human Resource Management and Employee Relations* (1st ed.). We Write Foundation.
- Kuncooro, Munajad. (2013). *Research Methods for Business and Economics*. Edition 4. Erlangga.
- Lestari, RA, & Santoso, SA (2022). *Public Services in Good Governance*.
- Millmore, M., Lewis, P., Saunders, M., Thornhill, A., & Morrow, T. (2007). *Strategic Human Resource Management*. Prentice Hall.
- Mishra, M., & Pandey, A. (2019). The impact of leadership styles on knowledge-sharing behavior: A review of the literature. *Development and Learning in Organizations*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLO-06-2018-0067>
- Nurchahyo, SA, & Wikaningrum, T. (2020). The Role of Knowledge Sharing, Learning Organization and Individual Innovation Capability on Employee Performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 21(2), 84. <https://doi.org/10.30659/ekobis.21.2.84-96>
- Partogi, SA, & Tjahjawati, SS (2019). The Effect of Knowledge Sharing on the Performance of Government-Owned Company Employees. *Journal of Business and Investment Research*, 5(3), 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.35313/jrbi.v5i3.1698>
- Qisty, S.N. (2021 CE). Implementation of knowledge sharing with the Binus Portal media at Bina Nusantara University. *Informatio: Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1(2), 167. <https://doi.org/10.24198/inf.v1i2.34055>

- Rosita, S., & Khalik, I. (2022). The Influence of Knowledge Management and Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at the Meranti Community Health Center, Merangin Regency. 4(1).
- Sari, AE (2022). The Influence of Knowledge Sharing on Employee Knowledge Management at the Regional Secretariat of Kerinci Regency, Mediated by Transfer of Training. 2(1).
- Sedarmayanti, & Nurliawati, N. (2012). Strategy for Strengthening Bureaucratic Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Corruption Prevention to Improve Service Quality. *Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 9(3).
- Sihite, M. (2018). Strategy for Building Highly Competitive Human Resources.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Combination Research Methods (Mixed Methods)*. CV. Alfabet.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methodologies and R&D*. Alfabet.
- Surasni, NK (2020). Study of the Impact of Leadership and Organizational Culture on Knowledge Sharing in the Regional Drinking Water Company on Lombok Island. *Mataram University Journal*, 9(2).
- Tupamahu, F.A.S., Pelamonia, M., & Pinoa, W.S. (2021). The Moderating Impact of Knowledge Sharing and Teamwork Behavior on Lecturer Productivity. *Journal of Educational Management and Supervision*, 5(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um025v5i12020p286>
- Ur Rehman, U., & Iqbal, A. (2020). Nexus of knowledge-oriented leadership, knowledge management, innovation and organizational performance in higher education. *Business Process Management Journal*, ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-07-2019-0274>
- Wibowo. (2014). *Behavior in Organizations*. Second Edition. PT Raja Grafindo Perdsada.